

THE IMPORTANCE OF USING MODERN TEACHING TECHNOLOGIES IN THE FORMATION OF CRITICAL THINKING

Allamov Shavkat Sharipovich

Urganch State University

Deputy dean for educational affairs of the Faculty of Pedagogy

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Abstract: This article highlights the importance of using critical thinking technologies in the educational process. At the same time, the specific features of this pedagogical technology are scientifically explained with the help of examples.

Key words: critical thinking, technology, pedagogical technology, educational process, ability, information.

At the same time, the policy of education and upbringing demands a new social order. Currently, our society requires people who can quickly rebuild and find a way out of a difficult situation by creating ideas. Deep changes taking place in modern education put the use of new technologies of education and training as a priority. Teachers have the opportunity to choose the teaching methods and technologies that, in their opinion, are the most optimal for building and designing the educational process. The purpose of the technology of development of critical thinking is to develop mental abilities of students, which are necessary not only for studying, but also for later life (ability to make clear decisions, work with information, analyze different aspects of events), etc. The formation of critical thinking skills in students depends on the organization of lessons by professors and teachers of higher education using educational technologies and creating favorable conditions for independent learning. Today, our pedagogues and parents are required not only to pay special attention to the education of young people, but also to talk with them more and at the same time encourage our young people to think critically. In this regard, several reforms are being implemented in the field of education in our country. As a clear example of this, Decree No. PF-5847 of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated 08.10.2019 "On approval of the concept of development of the Higher Education System of the Republic of Uzbekistan until 2030", Resolution No. PQ-4199 "On Measures for the Establishment of Presidential Schools" dated 06.11.2020 of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan "Additional Measures to Improve the Education System" We can see that Resolutions PQ-4884 serve to further develop and improve the education system.

The science of pedagogy has always been looking for ways to achieve high results in the educational process and has been constantly improving its tools, methods and forms. There was a desire to find some method or set of methods that would make it possible to achieve the intended goal. As a result, we can see that different methodologies have emerged. With the accumulation of pedagogical experience, new, more effective methods began to be created. In teaching practice, various ways, methods and forms of teaching are widely used. However, the search for a single effective (integral) approach to teaching is still being continued. The search for didactic approaches and didactic tools that can turn teaching into a unique manufacturing technological process continues.

Technological approach to the educational process - in order to facilitate the student's acquisition of knowledge, first of all, to divide the educational material (information) into interrelated parts, fragments (educational elements); then from education

Successive, step-by-step, consistent implementation of learning activities (actions, actions) to achieve the intended result; designed work requires the same execution of all actions.

The term pedagogical technology and the first developments in this field appeared in the USA in the 50s of the 20th century. After 15-20 years, pedagogical technology covered the education sector of all developed countries. In recent years, the scope of using pedagogical technology has been continuously expanding. The method and conditions of production are constantly changing rapidly and are making new demands on the education system.

On the one hand, what has been stated confirms the necessity of pedagogical technology, and on the other hand, it shows that it is a product of the acceleration of scientific and technical development. J. Braus and D. Wund define critical thinking as rational reflective thinking aimed at deciding what to believe and what to do. According to them, this is the squeak of reason, that is, how to think objectively and act logically, taking into account their point of view and the opinions of others, as well as letting go of their own prejudices. reflects ability. The technology of critical thinking appeared in America in the 80s of the 20th century. In Russia, the technology has been known since the late 90s and has another name: "Reading and writing for the development of critical thinking." L.S. Vygotsky about the zone of proximal development and the integral relationship between learning and the overall development of the child; K. Popper and R. Paul about the basics of formation and development of critical thinking; E. Brown and I. Beck on metacognitive learning; civil and legal education, etc. KM technology developers Kurtis Meredith, Charles Temple and Ginny Still translated the rules of these theories into the language of practice, brought their work to the level of pedagogical technology, distinguished its stages, methodological techniques and criteria. Therefore, their development can be used by a large number of teachers, who have achieved effective results in their work. Thus, critical thinking is not a separate skill, but a complex of many skills and abilities that are gradually formed during the child's development and education. If in the lessons children are not passive listeners, but constantly connect what they have learned with their practical experience (they are formed faster if they actively seek information). In addition, students should learn to question the reliability and validity of information, check the logic of evidence, draw conclusions, create new examples to use theoretical knowledge, make decisions, and learn cause and effect (teachers should also help with this).

Systematic inclusion of critical thinking in the educational process should form a special way of thinking and cognitive activity. The unique feature of this pedagogical technology is that during the learning process, the student builds this process himself, based on realistic and clear goals, monitors the direction of its development and determines the final result. On the other hand, the use of this strategy is aimed at developing the skills of working with information. In order to give children the opportunity to actively work with the acquired knowledge, the authors of the technology suggest building the lesson according to the usual scheme: "introduction - the main part - conclusion". Within technology, these stages have slightly different names and functions.

I stage. Make a call. This is for students to gain knowledge on the subject being studied, to activate their activities, and to motivate them for further work.

Tasks of this stage:

- updating and analyzing existing knowledge and ideas on the studied topic;
- arouse interest in him;
- to activate the student, express his thoughts in his own words and give him the opportunity to think purposefully;

During the implementation of the difficulty stage, the student "remembers" (makes assumptions) what he knows about the studied issue, organizes information before learning new material, and asks questions that he wants to get answers to. The teacher encourages students to remember what they already know about the subject being studied; exchange of conflicting ideas in groups, helps to identify and systematize information received from schoolchildren; asks a stranger to make guesses or predictions about a given topic. The information received during the call stage is listened to, recorded and discussed. Work is done individually, in pairs or in groups.

II stage. Understanding the content (getting new information).

It is directly aimed at maintaining interest in the subject while working with new information, and gradually moving from "old" knowledge to "new".

At the comprehension stage, direct contact with new information (text, film, paragraph material) is established. Work is done individually or in pairs. Group work should have two elements - individual exploration and exchange of ideas, and personal exploration, of course, precedes the exchange of ideas. Students read or listen to the text using active reading methods recommended by the teacher, taking notes when they understand new information. Children look for answers to questions and difficulties that have arisen before, prepare to analyze and discuss what they have heard or read.

Tasks of this stage:

- receiving new information;
- understand it (including the need to re-read part of the text if the student stops understanding it, understand the message, ask questions or write down what is unclear to clarify it in the future);
- connection of new information with own knowledge. Students consciously build bridges between old and new knowledge to create new concepts;
- maintaining the activity, interest and speed of movement created during the difficulty phase.

III stage. Reflection.

It is a matter of careful weighing, evaluation and selection. In the process of thinking, new information is assimilated and becomes one's own knowledge. It is noteworthy that it becomes the main goal of students' and teachers' activities. At the reflection stage, students become aware of their "I", the experience of their own actions, and the actions of other students and the teacher. They comprehensively understand the received information, summarize it, express their attitude to the studied material. Analysis, creative processing and interpretation of the studied data are carried out at the thinking stage. Work is done individually, in pairs or in groups.

Tasks of this stage:

- comprehensive understanding and generalization of the information obtained based on the exchange of ideas between students and the teacher;
- analysis of the entire process of studying the material;

Developing one's own attitude to the studied material and repeatedly problematizing it (a new "challenge"). In my opinion, such a lesson structure corresponds to the stages of human perception. First you need to speak, remember what you know about the topic, then learn new information, and then think about where you can apply what you have learned. With such an approach, not only the deeper acquisition of knowledge by children, but also the idea of material relations (within the same subject, interdisciplinary, theoretical and practical) is implemented, its construction by the child, students' determination of their own educational goals. creates the necessary internal motivation for the training process. Each stage has its own goals and tasks, as well as a set of characteristic methods aimed first at activating research and creative activity, and then at understanding and summarizing the acquired knowledge.

Based on the above, we can say that each student creates an integrated cognitive field that combines all available theoretical knowledge, practical information, skills and abilities. If a student thinks critically, he can easily enter any stage of the lesson. Each stage has its own methodological methods aimed at completing tasks. By combining them, the teacher can plan lessons according to the maturity level of the students, the purpose of the lesson and the amount of learning material. Each method and strategy of critical thinking is aimed at bringing out the creative potential of students. That is why it is important to organize the lesson based on modern educational technologies.

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